

DESIGN OF A VIVALDI ANTENNA FOR MICROWAVE IMAGING SYSTEMS OF ABLATION MONITORING

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Abstract

Thermal ablation treatment of cancer is increasingly adopted in the clinical practice, being minimally invasive and highly specific. However, a significant drawback of the technique is the lack of effective imaging modalities for monitoring the changes undergoing in the thermally treated tissue. In this respect, microwave imaging has been proposed as a possible candidate, owing to its portability, low-cost, non-ionizing nature, and capability to detect changes in dielectric properties of tissues induced by the temperature. In the microwave imaging system, the antenna is the most crucial part because it dictates the electromagnetic power delivered to the human body. In this paper, an antipodal Vivaldi antenna was designed for microwave imaging systems for ablation monitoring. The results of this study pave the way to an experimental assessment of the potential of microwave imaging as a modality to monitor thermal ablation treatments.

Index Terms – Microwave imaging, Vivaldi antennas, Electromagnetic devices, Ultra-wideband antennas

I. INTRODUCTION

Liver cancer is among the fifth leading cause of cancer death for men, and the seventh cause for women [1]. Liver cancer is recognized as a disease with an increased death rate every year [1]. Indeed, in the last 40 years, the overall death rate has doubled its number [1]. To improve the survival rate, the success of early-stage diagnoses and following clinical treatments is fundamental [2].

Microwave thermal ablation (MTA) is a treatment that destroys the tumor with a minimally invasive approach [3]. The clinical studies demonstrated that it has a good effect on small (less than 3 cm) to medium size lesions (3-5 cm) [4]. However, remotely monitoring of the ablation region during the treatment and detection of the ablation temperature remain distinct tasks for researchers [5].

The principle of MWI Microwave imaging (MWI) is based on processing the electromagnetic field scattered by the body to create images of the dielectric properties of tissues [6]. Given the significant thermal changes that electric properties of tissue undergo during ablation treatments [7], MWI is therefore viable for monitoring the progresses during the procedures [8]. Additionally, it has attractive features such as being harmless to human, compact-sized, and low-cost [6]. In particular, in MWI, the imaging resolution can be improved by increasing the number of antennas in the MWI system [9]. Hence, it is preferable to use compact antennas to allow a greater number of elements to be used.

In this paper, the design of a compact Vivaldi antenna to be used in the imaging system is presented. Vivaldi antennas are typically used for medical imaging applications thanks to their end-fire radiation pattern which allows high-density array arrangement [10]. Besides, Vivaldi antennas can easily achieve wideband performances without complex bandwidth enhancement designs [11]. The designed antenna is considered within a coupling medium to decrease antenna's dimensions, and maximize the electromagnetic power transfer to the human body.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Following a preliminary analysis for an experimental microwave imaging system for monitoring thermal ablation treatments of liver tumors [12], the most suitable operating frequency and coupling medium were identified by analyzing the transmitted power into the human abdomen using transmission line (TL) equivalence. The working frequency covers a bandwidth from 500 MHz to 3 GHz, while the suggested coupling medium has properties of $\epsilon_r=23$, $\sigma=0.07$ S/m. The antenna was designed using CST MICROWAVE STUDIO (Dassault Systèmes, France). CST is a software-based on the finite integration technique, applied to Maxwell's curl equation in the time domain. It is a marching-in-time procedure that simulates the propagation and interaction of electromagnetic waves in a region of space [13].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several Vivaldi antennas were studied, on different substrates and shapes. At last the antipodal Vivaldi antenna with RT/duriod 6010LM substrate (AVA-RT) (see FIG. 1) proved to be the most suitable one for this application. The antenna was designed by following [14], where an antenna working in air in the 3-10 GHz band is presented. Such antenna was chosen for its compact size and because it was designed for imaging purposes [14]. The design study was then aimed at taking the advantageous features of those antennas translating them into the

considered scenario, wherein the antenna is immersed in the coupling medium (not in the air) and operates at lower frequencies (500 MHz – 3 GHz). The thickness of this antenna substrates is 1.905 mm, plus a 17- μ m-thick conductive coating.

FIG. 1 Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna (AVA) geometry, $W=60\text{mm}$, $L=60\text{mm}$, $w_m=0.9\text{mm}$ (gray: metallic layer, pink: substrate)

FIG. 2 Simulated S_{11} parameters of the AVA-RT antenna fed by SMA connector and immersed in the matching medium ($\epsilon_r=23$, $\sigma=0.07\text{ S/m}$) with and without the presence of a planar multi-layer abdomen phantom

Finally, simulations were carried out to verify the antenna behavior in the presence of the human body. To this end, the AVA-RT, fed by a SMA connector and immersed in the matching medium ($\epsilon_r=23$, $\sigma=0.07\text{ S/m}$) was placed in contact to a 4-layer abdomen phantom consisting of skin, fat, muscle and liver. Based on average statistics, the thickness of each layers were set to be 2.3mm, 12.2mm, 20.2mm and 80mm, respectively [15][16]. FIG. 2 compares the antenna's matching in the presence and in the absence of the phantom. From the figure it can be

derived that the antenna keeps the matching when the human body is present.

FIG. 3 E-field distribution of AVA-RT antenna with the presence of a planar multi-layer abdomen phantom. The antenna is immersed in a matching medium ($\epsilon_r=23$, $\sigma=0.07$ S/m)

The E-field distributions on the yz plane (see reference system in FIG. 1 of the AVA-RT inside the matching medium ($\epsilon_r=23$, $\sigma=0.07$ S/m) and placed in direct contact with the multilayer phantom, are shown in FIG. 3, at 500 MHz, 1 GHz and 2 GHz. From the figure it is obvious that the electromagnetic power has good penetration inside the liver below 1 GHz. The penetration depth reduces at higher frequency. In particular, at 2 GHz only part of the liver can be detected.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, an antipodal Vivaldi antenna working in a medium of permittivity 23 and in direct contact with the human body was studied. Results show that the antenna keeps the matching when the human body is present.

Future work includes the realization of the coupling medium and of the antenna, and the measurement of antenna's characteristics to be compared with the numerical results.

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